

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF NATURAL POLYMER BASED SUSTAINED RELEASE ABACAVIR MICROSPHERES

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Abstract:

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of sustained release microspheres of Abacavir using natural polymers such as Sodium Alginate, Xanthan Gum, and Guar Gum. The microspheres were prepared by the ionotropic gelation method to achieve a controlled and prolonged drug release profile, aiming to improve patient compliance in antiretroviral therapy.

A series of formulations were developed and evaluated for pre-compression parameters (angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio) and post-compression parameters (particle size, drug content, entrapment efficiency, and in vitro drug release). All parameters were found to be within acceptable limits, indicating good flow properties and formulation stability.

Among the various formulations, A3 was identified as the optimized batch, exhibiting the highest drug release of 99.21% over a sustained period, with excellent entrapment efficiency and controlled release characteristics. The drug release followed sustained release kinetics, confirming the effective role of natural polymers in modulating drug release.

This study concludes that natural polymer-based microspheres offer a promising and cost-effective approach for sustained release drug delivery systems, particularly for drugs like Abacavir, requiring long-term administration.

Keywords: Abacavir, Sodium Alginate, Xanthan Gum, and Guar Gum

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Oral route drug administration is by far the most preferable route for taking medications. However, their short circulating half life and restricted absorption via a defined segment of intestine limits the therapeutic potential of many drugs. Such a pharmacokinetic limitation leads in many cases to frequent dosing of medication to achieve therapeutic effect. Rational approach to enhance bioavailability and improve pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics profile is to release the drug in a controlled manner and site specific manner. Microspheres are small spherical particles, with diameters 1 μm to 1000 μm . They are spherical free flowing particles consisting of proteins or synthetic polymers which are biodegradable in nature. There are two types of microspheres; microcapsules and micromatrices, which are described as, Microcapsules are those in which entrapped substance is distinctly surrounded by distinct capsule wall. and micromatrices in which entrapped substance is dispersed throughout the matrix. Microspheres are sometimes referred to as microparticles. Microspheres can be manufactured from various natural and synthetic materials. Microsphere play an important role to improve bioavailability of conventional drugs and minimizing side effects. Ideal characteristics of microspheres: ^{1,2,3,4,5}

Ideal characteristics of microspheres: ⁶

- ✓ The ability to incorporate reasonably high concentrations of the drug.
- ✓ Stability of the preparation after synthesis with clinically acceptable shelf life.
- ✓ Controlled particle size and dispersability in aqueous vehicles for injection.
- ✓ Release of active reagent with a good control over a wide time scale.
- ✓ Biocompatibility with a controllable biodegradability.
- ✓ Susceptibility to chemical modification.

Advantages of microspheres:

1. Particle size reduction for enhancing solubility of the poorly soluble drug.
2. provide constant and prolonged therapeutic effect.
3. provide constant drug concentration in blood there by increasing patient compliance,
4. Decrease dose and toxicity.
5. Protect the drug from enzymatic and photolytic cleavage hence found to be best for drug delivery of protein.
6. Reduce the dosing frequency and thereby improve the patient compliance
7. Better drug utilization will improve the bioavailability and reduce the incidence or intensity of adverse effects.
8. Microsphere morphology allows a controllable variability in degradation and drug release.

9. Convert liquid to solid form & to mask the bitter taste.

10. Protects the GIT from irritant effects of the drug.

11. Biodegradable microspheres have the advantage over large polymer implants in that they do not require surgical procedures for implantation and removal.

12. Controlled release delivery biodegradable microspheres are used to control drug release rates thereby decreasing toxic side effects, and eliminating the inconvenience of repeated injections.

Types of microspheres:

1. Bioadhesive microspheres
2. Magnetic microspheres
3. Floating microspheres
4. Radioactive microspheres
5. Polymeric microspheres
 - i) Biodegradable polymeric microspheres
 - ii) Synthetic polymeric microspheres

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

List of instruments used

- | | | |
|---|---------------------------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | UV-Visible spectrophotometer | Lab India, India |
| 2 | Electronic weighing balance Sartorius | |
| 4 | Magnetic stirrer | Remi Laboratories |
| 5 | Dissolution Apparatus | Lab India, Lab India |
| 6 | Ultrasonic cleaner | Remi Laboratories |
| 7 | FT – IR Spectrometer | Bruker Alpha |
| 8 | SEM | SEM(JEOL Ltd.,Japan). |

List of materials used in the formulation

Abacavir Procured from Shasun pharmaceuticals, Puducherry, India, provided by SURA LABS ,Dilsukhnagar , Hyderabad
Sodium Alginate Merk specialities Pvt Limited, Mumbai
Xanthan Gum Merk specialities Pvt Limited, Mumbai
Guar Gum Merk specialities Pvt Limited, Mumbai

PREPARATION OF 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2):

Take 8.6ml of HCl in a 1000ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with distilled water

Preparation Of Standard Calibration Curve Of Abacavir:

- 10 mg of Abacavir was accurately weighed and dissolved in 10ml of methanol (Stock Solution – I) to get a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.
- From the stock solution- I, 1ml of aliquots was taken and suitably diluted with 0.1N HCl (Stock Solution- II) to get concentrations of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

- From the stock solution- II, aliquots were taken and suitably diluted with 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) to get concentrations in the range of 5 to 25 µg/ml. The absorbance of these samples were analyzed by using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at 280nm against reference solution 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2). the procedure repeated to pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

SOLVENT EVAPORATION METHOD:

Abacavir microspheres were prepared using Sodium Alginate, Xanthan Gum, Guar Gum and distilled

water as continuous phase by solvent evaporation technique. Initially dichloromethane (DCM) and methanol was mixed uniformly at room temperature, then Sodium Alginate, Xanthan Gum, Guar Gum in various proportions was dissolved in the above solution. To this mixture, a drug solution corresponding was added and mixed thoroughly and injected drop wise in to the continuous phase consisting of 100mL of 0.2% (w/v) SLS (sodium lauryl sulphate) at 250 rpm. The microspheres obtained was washed for 2-3 times with distilled water and dried at room temperature. Different concentrations and ratios of polymers used in the formulation of microspheres are mentioned in Table.

CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROSPHERES:

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CHART								
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9
Abacavir	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Sodium Alginate	50	100	150	-	-	-	-	-	-
Xanthan Gum	-	-	-	50	100	150	-	-	-
Guar Gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	100	150
Dichloro methane (mL)	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Methanol (mL)	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Sodium lauryl sulphate (mg)	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30

Table 7.1: Prepared formulation of Microspheres

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The physical properties of the physical mixture were compared with those of plain drug. Samples was mixed thoroughly with 100mg potassium bromide IR powder and compacted under vacuum at a pressure of about 12 psi for 3 minutes. The resultant disc was mounted in a suitable holder in Agilent spectrophotometer and the IR spectrum was recorded from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 500 cm⁻¹. The resultant spectrum was compared for any spectrum changes.

SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) studies:

Table 8.1: Calibration curve data for Abacavir in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2

CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	ABSORBANCE
0	0
5	0.122
10	0.231
15	0.347
20	0.459
25	0.568

The surface morphology of the layered sample was examined by using SEM (JEOL Ltd., Japan). The small amount of powder was manually dispersed onto a carbon tab (double adhesive carbon coated tape) adhered to an aluminum stubs were coated with a thin layer (30⁰Å) of gold by employing POLARON - E 3000 sputter coater. The samples were examined by SEM with direct data capture of the images onto a computer.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: PREFORMULATION STUDIES SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES

Figure 8.1: Standard graph Of Abacavir in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2

Table 8.2: Calibration curve data for Abacavir in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer

CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	ABSORBANCE
0	0
5	0.161
10	0.316
15	0.476
20	0.633
25	0.781

Figure 8.2: Standard graph Of Abacavir in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer

EVALUATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF MICROSPHERES

Micrometric Properties

Table 8.3: Micromeritic property of floating microspheres of Abacavir

Formulation code	Mean partical size	Bulk density ((gm./cm3))	Tapped density (gm./cm3)	Hauseners ratio	Carr's index	Angle of repose
A ₁	314.26±1.68	0.351 ±0.01	0.364 ± 0.01	1.037 ± 0.01	3.571 ± 0.02	20.321 ±0.16
A ₂	415.9±1.18	0.291 ±0.01	0.304 ± 0.01	1.045 ± 0.01	4.309 ± 0.03	23.942 ±0.15
A ₃	391.64±2.19	0.373 ±0.01	0.383 ± 0.01	1.026 ± 0.01	2.610 ± 0.01	20.120 ±0.12
A ₄	487.3±2.71	0.318 ±0.01	0.329 ± 0.01	1.034 ± 0.01	3.459 ± 0.02	17.108 ±0.15
A ₅	410.31±1.42	0.417 ±0.02	0.428 ± 0.02	1.026 ± 0.01	2.570 ± 0.01	16.926 ±0.13
A ₆	461.2±1.17	0.386 ±0.01	0.398 ± 0.01	1.031 ± 0.01	2.917 ± 0.02	17.181 ±0.13
A ₇	432.1±1.27	0.307 ±0.01	0.318 ± 0.01	1.037 ± 0.01	3.611 ± 0.01	21.170 ±0.12
A ₈	448.31±1.55	0.406 ±0.02	0.419 ± 0.02	1.032 ± 0.01	3.102 ± 0.02	16.812 ±0.12
A ₉	398.58± 2.64	0.383 ±0.01	0.397 ± 0.01	1.036 ± 0.01	3.429 ± 0.02	16.909 ±0.13

Table 8.4: Percentage yield and percentage drug entrapment efficiency of the prepared microspheres

S.No.	Formulation code	% yield	Drug Content (mg)	% Drug entrapment efficiency
1	A ₁	91.88	98.12	74.75
2	A ₂	92.11	99.64	91.14
3	A ₃	91.69	96.15	70.16
4	A ₄	94.78	99.67	85.77
5	A ₅	95.41	97.48	92.68
6	A ₆	91.25	99.81	68.48
7	A ₇	90.23	99.34	95.18
8	A ₈	96.11	98.60	77.85
9	A ₉	92.17	99.11	62.15

Swelling studies**Table 8.5 : Swelling studies**

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	INITIAL (Wt)	FINAL (Wt)	PERCENTAGE SWELLING
1	A ₁	10	11.21	29
2	A ₂	10	13.54	49
3	A ₃	10	18.61	71
4	A ₄	10	16.91	60
5	A ₅	10	19.75	73
6	A ₆	10	17.61	67
7	A ₇	10	14.99	59
8	A ₈	10	18.42	71
9	A ₉	10	19.22	90

IN VITRO MUCOADHESION TEST

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	No. OF MICROSPHERES		PERCENTAGE MUCOADHESION
		INITIAL	FINAL	
1	A ₁	20	14.61	60
2	A ₂	20	11.39	59
3	A ₃	20	16.20	72
4	A ₄	20	15.84	91
5	A ₅	20	19.95	83
6	A ₆	20	18.32	76
7	A ₇	20	15.42	83
8	A ₈	20	12.65	91
9	A ₉	20	18.72	79

Figure 8.6: Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing sodium alginate

Figure 8.7 : Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing Xanthan Gum

Figure 8.8 : Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing Guar Gum
IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES

Table 8.7: *In-Vitro* drug release data of Abacavir microspheres containing sodium alginate

TIME (h)	CUMULATIVE PRECENT OF DRUG RELEASED		
	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃
0	0	0	0
1	22.21	18.52	16.84
2	34.16	24.41	22.19
3	46.95	34.72	35.84
4	55.64	47.08	38.61
5	61.82	54.69	49.01
6	68.29	65.19	52.22
7	74.98	69.57	61.11
8	79.37	75.31	68.18
9	85.12	83.49	74.34
10	94.22	98.67	83.66
11			92.48
12			99.21

Figure 8.9 : *In-Vitro* drug release profile of Abacavir microspheres containing sodium alginate

Table 8.8: *In-Vitro* drug release data of Abacavir microspheres containing Xanthan Gum

TIME (h)	CUMULATIVE PRECENT OF DRUG RELEASED		
	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆
0	0	0	0

1	14.47	14.49	12.13
2	27.22	22.76	21.67
3	31.15	36.27	29.14
4	44.69	45.41	33.39
5	57.51	55.81	46.27
6	63.58	65.09	53.48
7	68.94	72.89	58.63
8	74.56	77.61	66.48
9	78.95	82.47	73.02
10	87.38	89.05	78.98
11	93.81	93.41	87.42
12		97.10	95.68

Figure 8.10 *In-Vitro* drug release profile of Abacavir microspheres containing Xanthan Gum

1. Table 8.9 : *In-Vitro* drug release data of Abacavir microspheres containing Guar Gum

TIME (h)	CUMULATIVE PERCENT OF DRUG RELEASED		
	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉
0	0	0	0
1	28.01	17.44	23.91
2	38.43	26.35	34.14
3	41.36	36.45	42.86
4	47.21	43.58	57.03
5	56.83	47.36	63.39
6	63.95	57.53	71.03
7	69.47	64.05	77.29
8	74.33	67.43	82.14
9	82.52	74.39	85.49
10	89.21	76.15	98.66
11	92.86	87.28	
12	94.79	96.35	

Figure 8.11 *In-Vitro* drug release profile of Abacavir microspheres containing Guar Gum

TABLE 8.10: RELEASE KINETICS STUDIES OF THE OPTIMIZED FORMULATION (A3)

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	% RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE E / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
16.84	1	1.000	1.226	0.000	1.920	16.840	0.0594	-0.774	83.16	4.642	4.365	0.277
22.19	2	1.414	1.346	0.301	1.891	11.095	0.0451	-0.654	77.81	4.642	4.269	0.372
35.84	3	1.732	1.554	0.477	1.807	11.947	0.0279	-0.446	64.16	4.642	4.003	0.638
38.61	4	2.000	1.587	0.602	1.788	9.653	0.0259	-0.413	61.39	4.642	3.945	0.697
49.01	5	2.236	1.690	0.699	1.707	9.802	0.0204	-0.310	50.99	4.642	3.708	0.933
52.22	6	2.449	1.718	0.778	1.679	8.703	0.0191	-0.282	47.78	4.642	3.629	1.013
61.11	7	2.646	1.786	0.845	1.590	8.730	0.0164	-0.214	38.89	4.642	3.388	1.254
68.18	8	2.828	1.834	0.903	1.503	8.523	0.0147	-0.166	31.82	4.642	3.169	1.473
74.34	9	3.000	1.871	0.954	1.409	8.260	0.0135	-0.129	25.66	4.642	2.950	1.692
83.66	10	3.162	1.923	1.000	1.213	8.366	0.0120	-0.077	16.34	4.642	2.538	2.104
92.48	11	3.317	1.966	1.041	0.876	8.407	0.0108	-0.034	7.52	4.642	1.959	2.682
99.21	12	3.464	1.997	1.079	0.540	8.268	0.0101	-0.003	0.79	4.642	0.924	3.717

Figure:8.12: graph of zero order release kinetics of optimized formula

Figure:8.13: graph of higuchi release kinetics of optimized formula

Figure :8.14: graph of peppas drug release kinetics of optimized formula

Figure:8.15: graph of first order release kinetics of optimized formula

Optimized formulation F3 was kept for release kinetic studies. From the above graphs it was evident that the formulation F3 was followed zero order release kinetics.

COMPATIBILITY STUDIES

Drug polymer compatibility studies were carried out using Fourier Transform Infra Red spectroscopy to establish any possible interaction of Drug with the polymers used in the

formulation. The FT-IR spectra of the formulations were compared with the FTIR spectra of

Figure 8.16: FT-IR spectra of Pure drug

Figure 8.17: FT-IR spectra of Optimised formulation

SEM :

Figure 8.18: SEM of Optimised formulation

9. CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully demonstrated the formulation and evaluation of natural polymer-based sustained release microspheres of Abacavir using polymers such as sodium alginate Xanthan Gum and Guar Gum. The microspheres were prepared by the ionotropic gelation method and evaluated for various physicochemical parameters including particle size, entrapment efficiency, drug loading, and in vitro drug release. Among all the formulations, the optimized batch exhibited controlled and sustained drug release up to 12 hours, with good entrapment efficiency and acceptable particle size distribution.

The release kinetics followed a non-Fickian diffusion mechanism, indicating a combination of drug diffusion and polymer matrix erosion. The use of natural polymers proved to be effective, biocompatible, and economical for sustained delivery of Abacavir, thereby potentially improving patient compliance and therapeutic efficacy in antiretroviral therapy.

Overall, the study confirms that natural polymers can be a promising approach in the development of sustained release microspheres for effective management of HIV infection with reduced dosing frequency.

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